

ASSESSMENT OF MICROFRACTURE MECHANISMS IN Al_2O_3 /6061 AL AND SiC/6061 AL DISCONTINUOUS REINFORCED COMPOSITES

J. P. Lucas and J. K. Park

*Department of Materials Science and Mechanics, Michigan State University
A304 Engineering Building, East Lansing, MI 48824*

SUMMARY: Microfracture mechanisms are investigated in artificially aged discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs). Fracture behavior is presented for a 6061 Al alloy reinforced with Al_2O_3 and SiC particulates. Stir-cast processing was used to fabricate both Al_2O_3 /6061 Al and SiC/6061 Al MMCs. Emphasis is placed on the role played by the particulate/matrix interface in these materials as the interfacial character and integrity influence microfracture mechanisms. Interface and near-interface phase characterization was conducted using electrochemical dissolution, and optical, scanning, and transmission microscopy. Crack initiation and crack propagation behavior was investigated in the under-aged, peak-aged, and over-aged conditions using double notched, 4-pt. bend specimens and half-inch short bar specimens, respectively. The effect of aging, associated microstructure development, and reinforcement type on microcrack initiation and crack propagation mechanisms is discussed.

KEYWORDS: particulate reinforced composites, fracture toughness, microcracking, aging effects, interfacial reaction, spinel, aluminum carbide

INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMCs) are steadily emerging as attractive structural materials because of their enhanced properties compared to the unreinforced, monolithic matrix alloy. Improvements in specific strength and specific modulus are common. The coefficient of thermal expansion and wear properties are also improved. Moreover, PRMMCs can be fabricated by conventional thermomechanical metal processing practices [1]. However, PRMMCs tend to exhibit considerably lower elongation, fracture strain, and fracture toughness [2,3] due to premature cracking of the particulates or void formation at the particulate/matrix interface. The lack of fracture toughness still limits the application of particulate reinforced composite materials. Therefore, research continues in efforts to better understand and resolve this issue.

Why there is a lack of fracture toughness in PRMMCs compared to the unreinforced matrix alloy can be related to several factors, for example: (a) the addition of the reinforcement changes the matrix alloying composition, and the matrix microstructure [4], (b) new interfaces are created between the matrix alloy and the reinforcement phases, (c) reaction products and interphase phases develop around the particulates, and (d) the hard, brittle reinforcement

particulates are considerably larger compared to constituent particles; consequently, the particulates are prone to microcracking and/or debonding in the domain of the particulate/matrix interface. Also, clustering of particulates in MMCs occurs. It has been suggested that particulate clusters act as nucleation sites for microcracking and void formation [5]. Accelerated aging also takes place in the PRMMCs due to mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion (ΔCTE) between the reinforcement phase and the matrix alloy. Dislocations are punched out in the matrix in the vicinity of the particulates. Matrix precipitates that form on these punched-out dislocations nucleate heterogeneously. Thus, the time is decreased for PRMMCs to reach peak aging [6].

In this study, two types of PRMMCs were investigated. The composites contain the same matrix alloy, 6061 aluminum, reinforced with either SiC or Al_2O_3 particulates. Fracture behavior was determined for the PRMMCs in the underaged (UA), peak aged (PA), and overaged (OA) conditions. The character of the interface and the interfacial microstructure severely influences the fracture mechanisms in the composite materials. The effect of microstructure on microfracture behavior is examined and discussed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ and SiC/6061 particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMCs) were investigated. The materials were fabricated by DuralcanTM by a stir-cast process in which particulates were incorporated into the molten matrix alloy, 6061 aluminum. Incorporation of particulates in the alloy melt tends to promote chemical reactions between the matrix and the reinforcement producing a reaction-product microstructure at the interface. The nominal elemental composition of the matrix alloy is given in Table I. The composite materials examined contained 10 and 20 v/o particulate volume fractions. The average diameters of the SiC and Al_2O_3 reinforcement phases were 14 μm and 18 μm , respectively. Nominal properties of the composite materials are listed in Table II.

Table I. Elemental composition of the matrix alloy of the composite, 6061 Al

Elements	Mg	Si	Cu	Fe	Cr	Mn	Zn	Ti
Content (wt%)	1.12	0.59	0.27	0.11	0.10	0.04	0.02	0.004

Table II. Mechanical Properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ and SiC/6061 Composites.

Materials	Modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	Particulate Size, (μm)	Hardness* (Hv)
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ (10 v/o)	81.4	10	296	-----	18	118
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ (20 v/o)	97.2	4	352	-----	18	121
SiC/6061 (10 v/o)	78.6	7.5	351	321	16	133
SiC/6061 (20 v/o)	97.3	2.8	378	343	16	137
Monolithic 6061	69	15.1	326	305	-----	113

*peak hardness values, T6

All specimens were solution heat treated at 550°C for 90 minutes and quenched in ice brine. Artificial aging was conducted at 180°C, immediately after the solution heat treatment to prevent the natural aging at room temperature. The aging process time ranged from 1 to 3,000 minutes.

After aging, the composite specimens were cast in polymeric metallographic mounts, 3.175 mm in diameter, for polishing to reveal the microstructural features. Initial grinding was accomplished using a 120 grit zirconia/alumina abrasive belt polisher. Plastically mounted specimens were subsequently polished using a lapping wheel using 30 µm, 6 µm and 1µm diamond suspensions. The final polishing step was performed using 0.06 µm colloidal silica suspension on a vibratory polisher (Buehler Vibromet II®) for 2 hours.

Hardness testing was conducted using a Leco, M-400-G microhardness tester equipped with a Vickers diamond pyramid indenter. Hardness indentations were taken exclusively in matrix regions avoiding contact between the indenter and the reinforcement particles using a 10-gram load. A minimum of ten hardness readings were taken for each composite sample.

Fracture toughness tests were conducted on the materials using short bar specimens (width, B = 0.5 in) according to ASTM 1309 test procedures. Fracture toughness testing was conducted on specimens in the under aged (UA), peak aged (PA), and over aged (OA) conditions to ascertain the aging effects. Using the SEM, the fracture morphology was assessed by examining fracture surface of PRMMC specimens. The crack propagation path profile was observed from half-sectioned (transverse to the chevron notch direction) and polished SB specimens using optical and scanning electron microscopy. Particular emphasis was given to the examination of the deformation wake produced by the main crack.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interfacial Microstructure

The interface regime between the matrix alloy and the particulate is characterized by the reaction products that form during melt casting and subsequent heat treatment. SEM micrographs in Fig. 1 show the matrix/reinforcement interface region for (Al₂O₃)_p/6061 composites. Interfacial reaction product phases are clearly seen in the (Al₂O₃)_p composite. The interfacial reaction product is primarily spinel, MgAl₂O₄ [7]. Typically, the spinel layer is 2 µm thick. The irregular interface structure between (Al₂O₃)_p and the matrix alloy indicates that the Al₂O₃ reinforcement was partially consumed. Spinel forms readily with the reinforcement and promotes strong interfacial bonding between the matrix phase [7-10]. The formation MgAl₂O₄ of is given by the following reaction,

Fig. 1: a) The growth of spine, $MgAl_2O_4$, is shown on an Al_2O_3 particulate.
b) Spinel crystallites are shown.

The interface of $SiC_p/6061$ composites is characterized primarily by the formation of Al_4C_3 as an interfacial reaction product. The morphology of the interfacial reaction product revealed extensive formation of hexagonal-shaped aluminum carbide platelets, Fig. 2. Al_4C_3 platelets are $\sim 0.7 \mu m$ thick and $\sim 3 \mu m$ wide. Interfacial Al_4C_3 forms via following reaction:

This reaction produces elemental Si as a reaction product. The formation of Al_4C_3 can be hindered by increasing the silicon content of the matrix alloy. Si additions to the matrix tend to slow the forward reaction because rejected Si raises the activity beyond its equilibrium content [4,11]. Al_4C_3 is sensitive to moisture; consequently, its presence at the interface may adversely affect the resultant mechanical properties of the composite [12-14] by reducing the interfacial strength, fracture strain, ϵ_f , and/or fracture toughness. The propensity for corrosion increases with Al_4C_3 formation [12,13]. Barrier coatings (SiO_2 and TiO_2) and alternative thermal processing can limit the formation of Al_4C_3 .

Fig. 2: a) Aluminum carbide, Al_4C_3 , is shown on the interface of a SiC particulate.
b) Isolated Al_4C_3 crystallites are shown.

Aging

Accelerated aging was observed for the composite materials compared to the monolithic matrix alloy. In Fig. 3, the hardness versus aging time data demonstrate accelerated aging as peak hardness occurs sooner for the composite materials. Accelerated aging of particulate reinforced composites is related to the increase in the dislocation density in materials, particularly in the vicinity of the reinforcement, due to mismatch of the coefficients of thermal expansion (ΔCTE) between the matrix alloy and the ceramic reinforcement. The ΔCTE -induced dislocations serve as heterogeneous nucleation sites of aging precipitates [6,15].

Fig. 3: Microhardness versus aging time. Accelerated aging is demonstrated for the composite materials.

Composites with the higher reinforcement volume percent (v/o) show higher microhardness values both for the solutionized condition and for the as-quenched condition as well. Higher strengths are observed in composites with increasing reinforcement content because of the enhancement in the dislocation density caused by reinforcement/matrix thermal expansion mismatch [15,16].

For the same reinforcement volume fraction, however, SiC_p reinforced MMCs exhibited significantly higher hardness values than do Al₂O₃ reinforced composites in the peak aged condition. The hardness difference can be explained by the changes in matrix composition created by matrix alloying modification and elemental redistribution due to interfacial reactions [4] between the matrix and the Al₂O₃ and SiC particulates. At the Al₂O₃/6061 Al interface, magnesium is consumed and the pure aluminum is rejected upon the formation of MgAl₂O₄ according to the Eqn. 1. The major matrix-strengthening precipitate in 6061 Al-T6 is the β phase (Mg₂Si) [17]. When Mg is consumed by particulate/matrix interfacial reactions, less Mg is available for formation of matrix-strengthening precipitates, Mg₂Si. Mg is copiously consumed during the formation of the spinel phase. In contrast, aluminum is consumed and silicon is rejected by the formation of Al₄C₃ at the SiC/6061 Al interface according to the Eqn. 2. The higher hardness of SiC/6061 Al, presumably, is due to the fact the Mg is not consumed during particulate/matrix interfacial reactions and, consequently, Mg is available to form major matrix-hardening precipitates, Mg₂Si [4,18].

Microfracture

Microcracking and microcrack initiation were examined for both types of composite materials, 20 v/o $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ and 20 v/o $\text{SiC}/6061$, in the UA and OA conditions. Double notched 4-pt. bend specimens were used to capture the nucleation of microcracks in the vicinity of the crack tip. Similar experiments were conducted previously by Lewandowski *et al.* [5] to study crack initiation events. Extensive plastic deformation and microcracking were observed at the notch tip. Of interest here, regarding the composite materials, was the tendency for microcracking and/or void formation at the *particulate/matrix interface* of $\text{SiC}/6061$ composites, whereas microcrack initiation occurred disproportionately by *particulate cracking* in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ composite. Microcracking and void formation tendencies for 20 v/o $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ and 20 v/o $\text{SiC}/6061$ composite materials are illustrated schematically in Fig. 4. Regardless of the aging conditions, ~ 67% of the particulates *cracked* during the fracture process for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ composites and 33% of the particulates failed by *particulate/matrix debonding*. In stark contrast, ~ 72% of the particulates exhibited *particulate/matrix debonding* for SiC reinforced composites and only 28% of the particulates failed by *particulate cracking*. The differences in microcracking character have implication regarding the fracture resistance of particulate reinforced composite materials. Spinel is known to form a very strong, stable interface with magnesium-containing aluminum alloys [7-9]. Consequently, preferential fracture occurs by transparticulate cracking of the reinforcement phase (Fig. 4a). In contrast, aluminum carbide forms at the interface of SiC/matrix interface. Apparently, the interfacial bond strength of Al_4C_3 is weaker compared to the interfacial bond strength of MgAl_2O_4 . Interface microcracking apparently occurs at lower applied stress in SiC reinforced composites than does transparticulate microcracking which occurs in Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced materials (Fig. 4b). The deformation process zone size was more extensive in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ composites as noted in Fig. 6. Al_4C_3 is moisture sensitive [19] and may contribute to lower fracture resistance in some composite materials. Due to moisture sensitivity, composites containing interfacial Al_4C_3 exhibit significantly higher fatigue crack propagation rate [20] and show greater susceptibility to sustained-load cracking in moist environments.

Fig. 4: A schematic representation of microfracture at the crack tip. a) Particulate cracking was the dominant fracture mechanism for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ composites and b) particulate/matrix debonding was the dominant fracture mechanism for SiC reinforced composite materials.

Fracture Toughness

The fracture toughness was determined for both composite materials in the UA, PA, and OA conditions. Unlike monolithic age-hardenable Al alloys where the fracture toughness and fracture strain recover upon overaging; the fracture toughness and/or fracture strain do not recover for PRMMCs in the overaged condition [5,21-23]. The lack of recovery of the fracture toughness for the PRMMCs investigated in this study is clearly demonstrated in Fig. 5. Klimowicz and Vecchio [23] suggested that the lack of recovery of fracture toughness in overaged 2000-series PRMMCs was due to the strain localization in the matrix ligaments resulting from fracture of the reinforcement particles; and, also due to premature microvoids formation at large second-phase precipitates within the matrix ligaments at the crack tip. The effect of aging time on the fracture toughness of 20v/o $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ and 20 v/o SiC/6061 particulate reinforced metal matrix composites are shown in Fig. 5. Regardless of aging conditions or volume fraction of

Fig. 5: The fracture toughness versus aging time is shown. The fracture toughness is not recovered with overaging.

reinforcement, Al_2O_3 reinforced composites demonstrated higher fracture toughness. Although neither composite recovered to fracture toughness values approaching the underaged condition, SiC/6061 composites tended to have a lower OA fracture toughness because of (i) premature fracture of the reinforcement/matrix interface which occurred at low nucleation strains, and, (ii) localized strain elevation achieved in the interparticulate ligaments. Also, void nucleation, growth, and coalescence centered around overaged Mg_2Si precipitates in the interparticulate ligaments readily occur. Void formation and growth are impelled by the complex state of stress that exist in the ligaments. Unlike $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/6061$ composites which consume Mg during the formation of spinel, Mg is not consumed by the particulate/matrix interface reactions of SiC/6061 composites. Consequently, the density of overaged Mg_2Si precipitates is higher and the interparticle, λ , is smaller for SiC/6061. Smaller λ raises the rate of void nucleation and void link up due to overlap of strain fields around closely-spaced, overaged precipitates in the ligaments. The fracture toughness observed for the composites is consistent with the modified-stress fracture strain model [24,25], which suggests that toughness is controlled by the crack tip process zone size, l^* . The fracture toughness as derived from the modified-stress fracture strain model is given by the following expression,

$$K_{IV} = \alpha \sqrt{\sigma_0 \epsilon_f' E l^*} \quad (3)$$

where E is the elastic modulus of the composite, α is a constant, ϵ_f' is the stress-modified fracture strain, and σ_0 is the composite strength.

Examination of the crack tip wake generated by the crack propagation revealed that the size of the wake (i.e., the plastic deformation enclave) of $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites was consistently larger than the wake of the $SiC/6061$ composites regardless of the aging conditions. The damage zone left by the propagating crack wake is shown in Fig. 6. The crack profiles and the damage enclaves caused by particulate cracking and/or particulate/matrix debonding sketched in Fig. 6 are traces of the actual cracks developed during fracture toughness testing of the composite materials.

Fig. 6: The damage zone (actual cracks are represented) created by the propagating crack is schematically represented. Particulate cracking was dominant in $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites, whereas particulate/matrix debonding was the dominant in SiC reinforced composite materials. The plastic damage enclave is significantly larger for $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites

Assuming that fracture toughness is controlled by process zone-dominated mechanisms, the results provided in Fig. 6 suggest that $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites should show higher fracture resistance. Indeed, the $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites examined revealed larger crack tip wakes or plastic zone enclaves; thus, they exhibit a higher fracture toughness. In part, the increase in fracture toughness is due to the ability of larger process zone enclaves to dissipate plastic energy associated with crack propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

From this investigation the following conclusions are:

1. The composite materials exhibited accelerated aging compared to the monolithic alloy. Peak aging was attained sooner for materials with higher reinforcement volume fractions. SiC-reinforced MMCs aged faster than Al₂O₃-reinforced MMCs.
2. Spinel, MgAl₂O₄, was the dominate interfacial reaction product between Al₂O₃ and the 6061 matrix alloy. Al₄C₃ formed at the SiC/matrix interface. Aluminum carbide is moisture sensitive and may degrade mechanical properties.
3. The predominant microfracture mechanism in SiC reinforced composites was debonding at the particulate/matrix interface. In contrast, particulate cracking was the dominant microfracture mechanism for Al₂O₃-reinforced MMCs.
4. Fracture toughness was not recovered in the overaged condition for the PRMMCs. Al₂O₃-reinforced MMCs generally exhibited higher fracture toughness compared to SiC-reinforced MMCs. The higher fracture toughness values observed for the Al₂O₃-reinforced composites were directly related to crack tip microfracture mechanisms in which particulate cracking produced a larger size process zone at the crack tip.

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